

Common Fixed Point Results for Asymptotic Quasi-Contraction Mappings in Quasi-Metric Spaces

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Abstract

In this article, two new classes of pairs $\{T, f\}$ consisting of an asymptotic quasi-contraction T with respect to a map f are introduced. The existence and uniqueness of the common fixed point of such pairs $\{T, f\}$ is then established in the context of a quasi-metric space X , when T and f are weakly compatible. The theorems obtained rely on some conditions on the orbit $O_{T,f}(x, \infty)$ of T at points $x \in X$ with respect to f , and are in fact, improvements of previously known results in the literature of metric-types. An example is given to validate the results obtained.

Keywords: Asymptotic quasi-contraction, Meir-Keeler type mappings, Weakly compatible maps, Orbits, Jungck sequence.

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1 Introduction

There are many generalizations of the fundamental contraction mapping theorem established by Banach [1] which served as pivotal tool for solving problems in analysis and applied mathematics. For instance see [2-6]. One of the most general contraction mapping was introduced by Ciric [7] in 1971. In 2003, Kirk [8] introduced asymptotic contraction mapping which is a generalization of Banach contraction mapping and established the fixed point of the operator in a complete metric space under certain conditions. Asymptotic contraction map is for example, applied in dynamical system to solve analytical problems. Several works have been carried out in this regard, see [9, 10]. Meir-keeler [11] extended Banach contraction principle by proving the following result:

Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and f a self map of X .
Assume that for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $\delta > 0$ such that:
 $\epsilon \leq d(x, y) < \epsilon + \delta$ implies $d(fx, fy) < \epsilon$ for all $x, y \in X$.
Then f has a unique fixed point.

Suzuki [12] combined the works of Kirk [8] and Meir-Keeler [11] to introduce a class of map called asymptotic contraction of Meir-Keeler type (for short, ACMK). In 2008, Singh and Pant [13] extended the result of Suzuki [12] to more general maps. Our interest is in the result of Singh et al. [14] on maps that are called generalized asymptotic contraction of Meir-Keeler type (for short, GACMK).

Definition 1.1. Let (X, d) be a metric space, Y a subset of X , and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ two maps. The map T is called a generalized asymptotic contraction of Meir-Keeler type (in short GACMK) with respect to f if there is a sequence $\{\psi_n\}$ of self-maps on $[0, \infty)$ such that:

- (P₁) $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi_n(\epsilon) \leq \epsilon$ for all $\epsilon \geq 0$;
- (P₂) for each $\epsilon > 0$, there exist $\delta > 0$ and $\nu \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\psi_\nu(t) \leq \epsilon$ for all $t \in [\epsilon, \epsilon + \delta]$;
- (P₃) $d(T^n x, T^n y) < \psi_n(M(x, y))$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x, y \in X$ with $M(x, y) > 0$, where $M(x, y) = \max \left\{ d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), \frac{d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)}{2} \right\}$.

In the same reference, they stated the following result.

Theorem 1.2. Let (X, d) be a metric space and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ such that $T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$. Let T be a GACMK with respect to f . If $T(Y)$ or $f(Y)$ is a complete subspace of X , then T and f have a coincidence point. Further, if $Y = X$, then T and f have a unique common fixed point provided that T and f commute at a coincidence point.

Recall that the following definitions of coincidence points and weakly compatible mappings:

Definition 1.3. [15] Let X be a set and T and f be two self maps of X . A point x in X is called a coincidence point of T and f if and only if $Tx = fx$. We shall call $z := Tx = fx$ a point of coincidence of T and f .

Definition 1.4. [16] Two self maps T and f in a set X are said to be weakly compatible if they commute at their points of coincidence, that is, if $Tx = fx$ for some $x \in X$, then $Tfx = fTx$.

It should be noted that Definition 1.1 and Theorem 1.2 due to Singh et al. [14] pose a few problems:

1. for $x \in X$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the point $T^n x$ is not defined, except if $Y = X$;
2. the function f may not satisfy $f(x) = x$ for all $x \in Y$. Therefore, a sequence¹ $\{x_n\}$ such that $Tx_n = fx_{n+1}$ for all $n \geq 0$, may not satisfy $x_n = T^n x_0$ for all $n \geq 0$, an assumption which seem to have been used in several lines of their proof.

In this paper, our aim is to provide an amendment of the maps of Singh et al. [14] and establish an ensing common fixed point theorem in the framework quasi-metric spaces. The following are needed definitions in the setting of quasi-metric spaces:

Definition 1.5. [17] Let X be a non-empty set. A function $d : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is said to be a quasi-metric on X if for any $x, y, z \in X$ the following holds:

- (i) $d(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $x = y$;
- (ii) $d(x, z) \leq d(x, y) + d(y, z)$.

In such case, (X, d) is said to be a quasi-metric space.

Definition 1.6. [17-20] Let (X, d) be a quasi-metric space. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X is said to be:

- (i) forward-convergent to some $x \in X$ (called the forward limit) if $\forall \epsilon > 0 \exists N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N} : d(x_n, x) < \epsilon \forall n \geq N_\epsilon$; in other words, $\{x_n\}$ in X is forward-convergent to x if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x) = 0$.

¹The existence of such a sequence is discussed in subsection 2.1.

- (ii) backward-convergent to some $x \in X$ (called the backward limit) if $\forall \epsilon > 0 \exists N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}: d(x, x_n) < \epsilon \forall n \geq N_\epsilon$; in other words, $\{x_n\}$ in X is backward-convergent to x if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x, x_n) = 0$.
- (iii) convergent to some $x \in X$ if it is both forward-convergent and backward-convergent to x .
- (iv) forward Cauchy (or left K-Cauchy) if $\forall \epsilon > 0 \exists N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}: d(x_n, x_{n+k}) < \epsilon \forall n \geq N_\epsilon \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$.
- (v) backward Cauchy (or right K-Cauchy) if $\forall \epsilon > 0 \exists N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}: d(x_{n+k}, x_n) < \epsilon \forall n \geq N_\epsilon \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$.
- (vi) Cauchy (or p-Cauchy) if $\forall \epsilon > 0 \exists N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}: d(x_n, x_m) < \epsilon \forall n \geq N_\epsilon \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$. In other words, $\{x_n\}$ is Cauchy if it is forward Cauchy and backward Cauchy.

Definition 1.7. [21] *A quasi-metric space X is said to be complete if every Cauchy sequence in X is convergent in X .*

2 Generalized Asymptotic Contractions of Meir-Keeler type with respect to some functions

In the next section, we give ammend the definition of a generalized asymptotic contraction of Meir-Keeler type as proposed by Singh et al. [14], then prove a common fixed point theorem in complete quasi-metric space.

2.1 Jungck sequence and orbits with respect to f

Suppose X is a non-empty set, Y is a non-empty subset of X , and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ such that $T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$.

Choosing $x_0 \in Y$, one can define a Jungck sequence $\{x_n\}$ of points in Y such that

$$Tx_n = fx_{n+1}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.1)$$

If f is the inclusion map, that is, such that $f(x) = x$ for any $x \in Y$, then by repetitive application of (2.1), the sequence $\{x_n\}$ is such that $x_n = T^n x_0$, or more generally, $x_{n+k} = T^n x_k$ for any $n, k \geq 0$, with the convention that T^0 is the identity function on Y .

If f is not necessarily the inclusion map, and $x \in X$, the sequence of sets $\{(Tf^{-1})^n(x)\}_{n \geq 0}$ is defined as follows:

$$(Tf^{-1})^n(x) = \begin{cases} \{x\} & \text{if } n = 0 \\ \{Tu : f(u) = x\} & \text{if } n = 1 \\ \{Tu : f(u) \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(x)\} & \text{if } n > 1. \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

Given that $\emptyset \neq T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$, each $(Tf^{-1})^n(x)$ is non-empty and for $n > 1$,

$$(Tf^{-1})^n(x) = \left\{ Tu \mid \begin{array}{l} \exists u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-1} \in Y, f(u) = Tu_1, f(u_{n-1}) = x \\ \text{and if } n > 2, f(u_1) = Tu_2, \dots, f(u_{n-2}) = Tu_{n-1}, \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.3)$$

The Jungck sequence $\{x_n\}$ defined in (2.1) is such that for all $n, k \geq 0$, $Tx_{n+k} \in (Tf^{-1})^n(Tx_k)$, and in particular, $Tx_n \in (f^{-1}T)^n(Tx_0)$ and $Tx_{n+1} \in (Tf^{-1})(Tx_n)$.

Notice that when f is a bijection on Y , each $(Tf^{-1})^n(x)$ is the singleton. In the special case where $f(x) = x$ for all $x \in Y$, $(Tf^{-1})^n(x) = \{T^n x\}$ for each $n \geq 0$ and $x \in Y$.

In literature, orbits of self-maps and orbital completeness have been defined as follow:

Definition 2.1. [22] Let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a self mapping on a metric space. For each $x \in X$ and for any positive whole number n , define the sets:

$$O_T(x, n) = \{x, Tx, T^2x, T^3x, \dots, T^n x\}$$

and

$$O_T(x, \infty) = \{x, Tx, T^2x, T^3x, \dots, T^n x, \dots\}.$$

The set $O_T(x, \infty)$ is called the orbit of T at x and the metric space X is called T -orbitally complete if every Cauchy sequence in $O_T(x, \infty)$ is convergent in X .

The following definition is an extension of the concepts of orbits and orbital completeness for maps for which Jungck sequences are defined:

Definition 2.2. Let $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ be a two mappings defined on a subset Y of a set X , for which $T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$. For each $x \in X$ and for any positive whole number n , the set

$$O_{T,f}(x, n) := \{z \mid z \in (Tf^{-1})^i(x), 0 \leq i \leq n\} = \bigcup_{i=0}^n (Tf^{-1})^i(x)$$

will be called the n -orbit of T at x with respect to f , while the set

$$O_{T,f}(x, \infty) := \{z \mid z \in (Tf^{-1})^i(x), i \geq 0\} = \bigcup_{i=0}^{\infty} (Tf^{-1})^i(x)$$

will be called the orbit of orbit of T at x with respect to f .

If X is endowed with a quasi-metric d , then X is called $\{T, f\}$ -orbitally complete if every Cauchy sequence in $O_{T,f}(x, \infty)$ is convergent in X .

It immediately follows that the well-known concepts of orbits and orbital completeness of a map T are obtained when $f(x) = x$ for all $x \in Y$. More precisely, $O_{T,f}(x, n)$ becomes $O_T(x, n)$ and $O_{T,f}(x, \infty)$ becomes $O_T(x, \infty)$.

2.2 GACMK re-introduced

We can then re-introduce the definition of Generalized Asymptotic Contraction of Meir-Keeler type (GACMK) with respect to a function f :

Definition 2.3. Let (X, d) be a quasi-metric space, Y a subset of X , and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ two mappings. The map T is called generalized asymptotic contraction of Meir - Keeler type (GACMK, simply) with respect to f if there exists a sequence $\{\psi_n\}$ of functions from $[0, \infty)$ into itself satisfying the following:

$$(G_1) \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi_n(\epsilon) \leq \epsilon \text{ for all } \epsilon > 0;$$

$$(G_2) \text{ for each } \epsilon > 0 \text{ there exist } \delta > 0 \text{ and } \nu \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } \psi_\nu(t) \leq \epsilon \text{ for all } t \in [\epsilon, \epsilon + \delta];$$

$$(G_3) \text{ For all } n \in \mathbb{N}, \text{ and } x, y \in Y \text{ such that } M(x, y) > 0,$$

$$d(u, v) < \psi_n(M(x, y)), \tag{2.4}$$

for all $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$, $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$, where:

$$M(x, y) = \max \left\{ d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), \frac{d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)}{2} \right\}. \tag{2.5}$$

Remark 2.4.

1. It should be noted that Definition 2.3 differs with Definition 1.1 proposed by Singh et al. [14] in that the inequality (2.4), $d(u, v) < \psi_n(M(x, y))$, holds for any $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$ and $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$ rather than for $u = T^n x$ and $v = T^n y$ (which would only exist if $Y = X$).

2. Suppose $f(x) = x$ for all $x \in Y$, then for any $x, y \in Y$, we have that

$$M(x, y) = \max \left\{ d(x, y), d(x, Tx), d(y, Ty), \frac{d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)}{2} \right\}$$

and $(u, v) = (T^n x, T^n y)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$, and $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$. Under this condition, for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $d(T^n x, T^n y) < \psi_n(M(x, y))$ for $x, y \in Y$ such that $M(x, y) > 0$, and

- (i) if $\max\{d(x, y), d(x, Tx), d(y, Ty), d(x, Ty), d(y, Tx)\} = d(x, y)$ in (iii) of Definition 2.3, T becomes an asymptotic contraction of Meir-Keeler type (or simply, ACMK) discussed in by Suzuki [12];
- (ii) the case where $M(x, y) = \max\{d(x, y), d(x, Tx), d(y, Ty)\}$ for all $x, y \in X$ is discussed by Singh and Pant [13].

2.3 A fixed point theorem

Now we prove the following theorem on the existence and uniqueness of the common fixed point of a pair $\{T, f\}$ where T is a GACMK with respect to f .

Theorem 2.5. *Let (X, d) be a quasi-metric space and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ such that $T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$. Let T be a GACMK with respect to f , i.e., such that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x, y \in Y$ such that $M(x, y) > 0$,*

$$d(u, v) < \psi_n(M(x, y))$$

for any $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$ and $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$, where

$$M(x, y) = \max \left\{ d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), \frac{d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)}{2} \right\}.$$

and $\{\psi_n\}$ is a sequence of self-maps on $[0, \infty)$ such that:

(G₁) $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi_n(\epsilon) \leq \epsilon$ for all $\epsilon \geq 0$;

(G₂) for each $\epsilon > 0$, there exist $\delta > 0$ and $\nu \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\psi_\nu(t) \leq \epsilon$ for all $t \in [\epsilon, \epsilon + \delta]$.

Suppose further that:

(G₄) any two distinct elements z_1, z_2 in $O_{T,f}(x, \infty)$, $\frac{d(z_1, z_2)}{2} < d(z_2, z_1)$.

If $T(Y)$ or $f(Y)$ is a complete subspace of X , then T and f have a coincidence point. Further, if $Y = X$, then T and f have a unique common fixed point provided that T and f commute at a coincidence point.

Proof. Let $x_0 \in Y$ be arbitrary chosen. Since $T(Y) \subset f(Y)$, we can define a Jungck sequence $\{x_n\}$ of points in Y , and a sequence $\{y_n\}$ in X such that

$$y_n = Tx_n = fx_{n+1}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

This means that

$$Tx_{n+k} \in (Tf^{-1})^n(Tx_k) \quad \forall n, k \geq 0, \tag{2.6}$$

and that

$$d(Tx_{n+i}, Tx_{n+j}) < \psi_{n+1}(M(x_i, x_j)) \quad \text{for all } n \geq 0 \text{ and } i, j \text{ with } M(x_i, x_j) > 0. \quad (2.7)$$

First step: We prove by cases that T and f have a coincidence point if $T(Y)$ or $f(Y)$ is complete.

If there is $n \geq 0$ such that $Tx_n = Tx_{n+1}$, then x_{n+1} is a coincidence point of T and f , since $fx_{n+1} = Tx_{n+1}$. Suppose now that $Tx_n \neq Tx_{n+1}$ for all $n \geq 0$.

For any $n \geq 0$, we have $d(fx_{n+1}, Tx_{n+1}) = d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}) > 0$, hence $M(x_i, x_j) > 0$ for any distinct $i, j \geq 0$.

For any $n \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}) &< \psi_1(M(x_n, x_{n+1})) \\ &\leq M(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &= \max \left\{ d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n), d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}), \frac{d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_{n+1})}{2} \right\} \\ &\leq \max \{ d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n), d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}) \}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

hence for all $n \geq 1$,

$$\begin{cases} M(x_n, x_{n+1}) &= d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n) \\ d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}) &< d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n). \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

Thus, the sequence $\{d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1})\}_{n \geq 0}$ is decreasing and bounded below hence converges to some $\alpha \geq 0$, and $d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}) > \alpha$ for all $n \geq 0$.

Suppose $\alpha > 0$. Since $0 < \alpha < d(Tx_0, Tx_1)$, there are $\delta_1 > 0$ and $\mu_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\psi_{\mu_1}(t) \leq \alpha$ for all $t \in [\alpha, \alpha + \delta_1]$. By definition of α , there is $\mu_2 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $M(x_{\mu_2}, x_{\mu_2+1}) = d(Tx_{\mu_2-1}, Tx_{\mu_2}) < \alpha + \delta_1$. Therefore, $d(Tx_{\mu_2+\mu_1-1}, Tx_{\mu_2+\mu_1}) < \psi_{\mu_1}(M(x_{\mu_2}, x_{\mu_2+1})) \leq \alpha$, a contradiction. Thus $\alpha := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}) = 0$.

Next we show that $\{Tx_n\}$ is forward-Cauchy sequence. Assuming $\{y_n\}$ is not a forward-Cauchy sequence, there exists $\beta > 0$ and increasing sequences $\{m_k\}$ and $\{n_k\}$ of positive integers such that for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $m_k < n_k$, $d(Tx_{m_k}, Tx_{n_k}) \geq \beta$ and $d(Tx_{m_k}, Tx_{n_k-1}) < \beta$. By the triangle inequality,

$$d(Tx_{m_k}, Tx_{n_k}) \leq d(Tx_{m_k}, Tx_{n_k-1}) + d(Tx_{n_k-1}, Tx_{n_k}),$$

and as $k \rightarrow \infty$, $d(Tx_{m_k}, Tx_{n_k}) \rightarrow \beta$. We also have that:

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx_{m_k}, Tx_{n_k}) &< \psi_1(M(x_{m_k}, x_{n_k})) \\ &= \psi_1 \left(\max \left\{ d(Tx_{m_k-1}, Tx_{n_k-1}), d(Tx_{m_k-1}, Tx_{m_k}), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. d(Tx_{n_k-1}, Tx_{n_k}), \frac{d(Tx_{m_k-1}, Tx_{n_k}) + d(Tx_{n_k-1}, Tx_{m_k})}{2} \right\} \right), \end{aligned}$$

hence as $k \rightarrow \infty$, $\beta \leq \psi_1(\beta) < \beta$, a contradiction. Thus $\{Tx_n\}$ is a forward-Cauchy sequence.

We may prove similarly that $\{Tx_n\}$ is a backward-Cauchy sequence. Indeed, for any $n \geq 0$, we have $d(Tx_{n+1}, fx_{n+1}) = d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n) > 0$, hence $M(x_i, x_j) > 0$ for any distinct $i, j \geq 0$. For any $n \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n) &< \psi_1(M(x_{n+1}, x_n)) \\ &\leq M(x_{n+1}, x_n) \\ &= \max \left\{ d(Tx_n, Tx_{n-1}), d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n), \frac{d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_{n-1})}{2} \right\} \\ &\leq \max \{ d(Tx_n, Tx_{n-1}), d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n) \}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

hence for all $n \geq 1$,

$$\begin{cases} M(x_{n+1}, x_n) &= d(Tx_n, Tx_{n-1}) \\ d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n) &< d(Tx_n, Tx_{n-1}). \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

The sequence $\{d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n)\}_{n \geq 0}$ is decreasing and bounded below hence converges to some $\gamma \geq 0$, and $d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n) > \gamma$ for all $n \geq 0$. In fact, $\gamma = 0$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n) = 0$. To see this, assume $\gamma > 0$. Since $0 < \gamma < d(Tx_1, Tx_0)$, there are $\eta_1 > 0$ and $\zeta_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\psi_{\zeta_1}(t) \leq \gamma$ for all $t \in [\gamma, \gamma + \eta_1]$. By definition of γ , there is $\zeta_2 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $M(x_{\zeta_2+1}, x_{\zeta_2}) = d(Tx_{\zeta_2}, Tx_{\zeta_2-1}) < \gamma + \eta_1$. Therefore, $d(Tx_{\zeta_2+\zeta_1}, Tx_{\zeta_2+\zeta_1-1}) < \psi_{\zeta_1}(M(x_{\zeta_2+1}, x_{\zeta_2})) \leq \gamma$, a contradiction.

If one assumes $\{Tx_n\}$ is not a backward-Cauchy sequence, there would exist $\epsilon > 0$ and increasing sequences $\{m_k\}$ and $\{n_k\}$ of positive integers such that for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $m_k < n_k$, $d(Tx_{n_k}, Tx_{m_k}) \geq \epsilon$ and $d(Tx_{n_k-1}, Tx_{m_k}) < \epsilon$. By the triangle inequality,

$$d(Tx_{n_k}, Tx_{m_k}) \leq d(Tx_{n_k}, Tx_{n_k-1}) + d(Tx_{n_k-1}, Tx_{m_k}),$$

and as $k \rightarrow \infty$, $d(Tx_{n_k}, Tx_{m_k}) \rightarrow \epsilon$. Therefore, letting $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the following

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx_{n_k}, Tx_{m_k}) &< \psi_1(M(x_{n_k}, x_{m_k})) \\ &= \psi_1 \left(\max \left\{ d(Tx_{n_k-1}, Tx_{m_k-1}), d(Tx_{n_k-1}, Tx_{n_k}), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. d(Tx_{m_k-1}, Tx_{m_k}), \frac{d(Tx_{n_k-1}, Tx_{m_k}) + d(Tx_{m_k-1}, Tx_{n_k})}{2} \right\} \right), \end{aligned}$$

hence as $k \rightarrow \infty$, $\beta \leq \psi_1(\beta) < \beta$, a contradiction. Thus $\{Tx_n\}$ is a backward-Cauchy sequence.

The sequence $\{Tx_n\}$ is both forward and backward Cauchy hence it is a Cauchy sequence.

If $f(Y)$ is complete, then the Cauchy sequence $\{Tx_n\}$ as a Cauchy sequence in $f(Y)$ converges to some element $f(u)$, where $u \in Y$. If there is $n_0 \geq 0$ such that $M(x_{n_0}, u) = 0$, then $fu = Tu$. Otherwise, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx_n, Tu) &< \psi_1(M(x_n, u)) \\ &= \psi_1 \left(\max \left\{ d(fx_n, fu), d(fx_n, Tx_n), d(fu, Tu), \frac{d(fx_n, Tu) + d(fu, Tx_n)}{2} \right\} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Taking $n \rightarrow \infty$, $d(fu, Tu) \leq \psi_1(\max\{d(fu, Tu)\})$, hence $d(fu, Tu) = 0$ and $fu = Tu$. The same conclusion is easily obtained if $T(Y)$ is assumed to be complete.

Second step: We prove that if $Y = X$, then T and f have a unique common fixed point provided T and f are weakly compatible.

$Tu = fu$ and T and f are weakly compatible, hence $Tfu = fTu$ and in fact, $TTu = Tfu = fTu = ffu$.

Suppose $TTu \neq Tu$. Then $M(u, Tu) > 0$ and since $Tu \in (Tf^{-1})^0(Tu)$ and $T(Tu) \in (Tf^{-1})^0(T(Tu))$,

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tu, TTu) &\leq \psi_1(M(u, Tu)) \\ &= \psi_1 \left(\max \left\{ d(fu, fTu), d(fu, Tu), d(fTu, TTu), \frac{d(fu, TTu) + d(fTu, Tu)}{2} \right\} \right) \\ &= \psi(\max\{d(Tu, TTu)\}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $d(Tu, TTu) = 0$, so $Tu = TTu = fTu$. Therefore, $z := Tu$ is a common fixed point of T and f .

To prove the uniqueness of the common fixed point of T and f , we assume v to be another common fixed point of T and f such that $Tu \neq v$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} d(z, v) = d(Tz, Tv) &\leq \psi_1(M(z, v)) \\ &\leq \psi_1 \left(\max \left\{ d(fz, fv), d(fz, Tz), d(fv, Tv), \frac{d(fv, Tz) + d(fz, Tv)}{2} \right\} \right) \\ &= \psi_1 \left(\max \left\{ d(z, v), \frac{d(v, z) + d(z, v)}{2} \right\} \right) \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$d(z, v) < \frac{d(v, z) + d(z, v)}{2}. \quad (2.12)$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} d(v, z) = d(Tv, Tz) &\leq \psi_1(M(v, z)) \\ &\leq \psi_1\left(\max\left\{d(fv, fz), d(Tv, fv), d(Tz, fz), \frac{d(Tv, fz) + d(Tz, fv)}{2}\right\}\right) \\ &\leq \psi_1\left(\max\left\{d(v, z), \frac{d(v, z) + d(z, v)}{2}\right\}\right) \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$d(v, z) < \frac{d(v, z) + d(z, v)}{2}. \quad (2.13)$$

Combining inequalities (2.12) and (2.13), $d(v, z) + d(z, v) < d(v, z) + d(z, v)$, a contradiction. Thus $z = v$: the common fixed point is unique. \square

Note that Theorem 2.5 provides an erratum to the result of Singh et al. [14] in metric spaces:

Theorem 2.6. *Let (X, d) be a metric space and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ such that $T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$. Let T be a GACMK with respect to f , i.e., such that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x, y \in Y$ such that $M(x, y) > 0$,*

$$d(u, v) < \psi_n(M(x, y))$$

for any $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$ and $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$, where

$$M(x, y) = \max\left\{d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), \frac{d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)}{2}\right\}.$$

and $\{\psi_n\}$ is a sequence of self-maps on $[0, \infty)$ such that:

$$(P_1) \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi_n(\epsilon) \leq \epsilon \text{ for all } \epsilon \geq 0;$$

$$(P_2) \text{ for each } \epsilon > 0, \text{ there exist } \delta > 0 \text{ and } \nu \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } \psi_\nu(t) \leq \epsilon \text{ for all } t \in [\epsilon, \epsilon + \delta].$$

If $T(Y)$ or $f(Y)$ is a complete subspace of X , then T and f have a coincidence point. Further, if $Y = X$, then T and f have a unique common fixed point provided that T and f commute at a coincidence point.

Proof. The Theorem follows from Theorem 2.5. The condition (G_4) is automatically satisfied in a metric space given the symmetry of a metric. \square

A careful analysis of the proof of Theorem 2.5 reveals that condition (G_4) is not necessary if $M(x, y)$ is replaced with $\max\{d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty)\}$. Therefore, we have the following result:

Theorem 2.7. *Let (X, d) be a quasi-metric space and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ such that $T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$. Let T be a GACMK with respect to f , i.e., such that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x, y \in Y$ such that $\{d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty)\} \neq \{0\}$,*

$$d(u, v) < \psi_n(\max\{d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty)\})$$

for any $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$ and $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$, where

$$M(x, y) = \max\left\{d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), \frac{d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)}{2}\right\}.$$

and $\{\psi_n\}$ is a sequence of self-maps on $[0, \infty)$ such that:

$$(G_1) \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi_n(\epsilon) \leq \epsilon \text{ for all } \epsilon \geq 0;$$

$$(G_2) \text{ for each } \epsilon > 0, \text{ there exist } \delta > 0 \text{ and } \nu \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } \psi_\nu(t) \leq \epsilon \text{ for all } t \in [\epsilon, \epsilon + \delta].$$

If $T(Y)$ or $f(Y)$ is a complete subspace of X , then T and f have a coincidence point. Further, if $Y = X$, then T and f have a unique common fixed point provided that T and f commute at a coincidence point.

3 A fixed point theorem for asymptotic quasi-contractions

In this section, we consider the case where there is a real number $c \in (0, 1)$ such that $\psi_n(t) = ct$ for all $t \in [0, \infty)$ and every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, albeit, $M(x, y)$ is further relaxed.

Theorem 3.1. *Let (X, d) be a quasi-metric space and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ such that $T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$. Suppose also that there is $c \in (0, 1)$ such that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x, y \in Y$ with $M(x, y) > 0$,*

$$d(u, v) \leq cM(x, y) \tag{3.1}$$

for any $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$ and $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$, where

$$M(x, y) = \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} d(fx, fy), d(fy, fx), d(fx, Tx), d(Tx, fx), d(fy, Ty), \\ d(Ty, fy), d(fx, Ty), d(Ty, fx), d(fy, Tx), d(Tx, fy) \end{array} \right\}. \tag{3.2}$$

If $T(Y)$ or $f(Y)$ is $\{T, f\}$ -orbitally complete, then T and f have a coincidence point. Further, if $Y = X$, then T and f have a unique common fixed point provided that T and f commute at a coincidence point.

Proof. Let $x_0 \in Y$ be arbitrary chosen. Since $T(Y) \subset f(Y)$, we can define a Jungck sequence $\{x_n\}$ of points in Y such that

$$Tx_n = fx_{n+1}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Step 1: Suppose $T(Y)$ or $f(Y)$ is $\{T, f\}$ -orbitally complete. We want to show that T and f have a coincidence point. We distinguish two cases:

Case 1: If there is $n \geq 0$ such that $Tx_n = Tx_{n+1}$, then x_{n+1} is a coincidence point of T and f , since $fx_{n+1} = Tx_{n+1}$.

Case 2: Suppose now that $Tx_n \neq Tx_{n+1}$ for all $n \geq 0$. For any $n \geq 0$, we have $d(fx_{n+1}, Tx_{n+1}) = d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}) > 0$, hence $M(x_i, x_j) > 0$ for any distinct $i, j \geq 0$.

If we let $D(x, y) = \max \{d(x, y), d(y, x)\}$ for all $x, y \in X$, the pair (X, D) is a metric space and conditions (3.12) and (3.4) become for all $x, y \in X$ such that $N(x, y) > 0$:

$$D(u, v) \leq cN(x, y) \tag{3.3}$$

for all $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$ and $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$, where

$$N(x, y) = \max \{D(fx, fy), D(fx, Tx), D(fy, Ty), D(fx, Ty), D(fy, Tx)\}. \tag{3.4}$$

Let $n \geq 2$ and $i, j \geq 1$ such that $1 \leq i < j \leq n$.

Since $Tx_i \in (Tf^{-1})^{i-1}(Tx_1)$, $Tx_j \in (Tf^{-1})^{j-1}(Tx_{j-i+1})$, and $M(x_1, x_{j-i+1}) > 0$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} D(Tx_i, Tx_j) &\leq cN(x_1, x_{j-i+1}) \\ &\leq c \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} D(Tx_0, Tx_{j-i}), D(Tx_0, Tx_1), D(Tx_{j-i}, Tx_{j-i+1}), \\ D(Tx_0, Tx_{j-i+1}), D(Tx_{j-i}, Tx_1) \end{array} \right\} \\ &\leq c \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_0, n)), \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

where

$$\mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_0, n)) := \sup \{D(z_1, z_2) : z_1, z_2 \in O_{T,f}(Tx_0, n)\}.$$

In particular, for all $n \geq 2$,

$$D(Tx_1, Tx_n) \leq c \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_0, n)).$$

Given $n \geq 1$, $O_{T,f}(Tx_0, n)$ is finite hence, there is $m \in \{2, 3, \dots, n\}$ such that

$$D(Tx_0, Tx_m) = \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_0, n)). \tag{3.6}$$

Now, for $n \geq 3$,

$$\begin{aligned} D(Tx_1, Tx_m) &\leq cN(x_1, x_m) \\ &= c \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} D(Tx_0, Tx_{m-1}), D(Tx_0, Tx_1), D(Tx_{m-1}, Tx_m), \\ D(Tx_0, Tx_m), D(Tx_{m-1}, Tx_1) \end{array} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

hence $m > 2$,

$$\max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} D(Tx_0, Tx_{m-1}), D(Tx_0, Tx_1), D(Tx_{m-1}, Tx_m), \\ D(Tx_0, Tx_m), D(Tx_{m-1}, Tx_1) \end{array} \right\} = D(Tx_0, Tx_m),$$

so $D(Tx_1, Tx_m) \leq cD(Tx_0, Tx_m)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} D(Tx_0, Tx_m) &\leq D(Tx_0, Tx_1) + D(Tx_1, Tx_m) \\ &\leq D(Tx_0, Tx_1) + cD(Tx_0, Tx_m). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$D(Tx_0, Tx_m) \leq \frac{1}{1-c} D(Tx_0, Tx_1). \quad (3.7)$$

From (3.6) and (3.7), the sequence $\{\mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_0, n))\}_{n \geq 3}$ is bounded above; since it is also increasing, it converges to the positive number $\mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_0, \infty))$.

To show that $\{Tx_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence, let $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$ with $n < m$. Since $Tx_n \in (Tf^{-1})^0(Tx_n)$, $Tx_m \in (Tf^{-1})^0(Tx_m)$, and $M(x_n, x_m) > 0$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} D(Tx_n, Tx_m) &\leq cN(x_n, x_m) \\ &\leq c \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} D(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_{m-1}), D(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n), \\ D(Tx_{m-1}, Tx_m), D(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_m), D(Tx_{m-1}, Tx_n) \end{array} \right\} \\ &\leq c \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_{n-1}, m - n + 1)). \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

Repeating the argument that led to (3.6), there is $m_1 \in \{2, 3, \dots, m - n + 1\}$ such that

$$D(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_{n-1+m_1}) = \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_{n-1}, m - n + 1)). \quad (3.9)$$

Thus, from (3.8),

$$\begin{aligned} D(Tx_n, Tx_m) &\leq c \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_{n-1}, m - n + 1)) \\ &= cD(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_{n-1+m_1}) \\ &\leq c^2 \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_{n-2}, m_1 + 1)) \\ &\leq c^2 \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_{n-2}, m - n + 2)) \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Repeating the process, one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} D(Tx_n, Tx_m) &\leq c^n \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_0, m)) \\ &\leq c^n \mathbf{diam}(O_{T,f}(Tx_0, \infty)). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, as $n, m \rightarrow \infty$, $D(Tx_n, Tx_m) \rightarrow 0$, hence $\{Tx_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . $f(Y)$ or $T(Y)$ being $\{T, f\}$ -orbitally complete, $\{Tx_n\}$ has a limit, say fu , where $u \in X$. Suppose that $fu \neq Tu$; then $N(u, x_n) > 0$ for all $n \geq 1$, and

$$\begin{aligned} D(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq cN(u, x_n) \\ &= c \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} D(fu, Tx_{n-1}), D(fu, Tu), D(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n), \\ D(Tx_{n-1}, Tu), D(fu, Tx_n) \end{array} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

Thus, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, $D(Tu, fu) \leq cD(fu, Tu)$, a contradiction. Thus $D(Tu, fu) = 0$ and $Tu = fu$. u is a coincidence point of T and f .

Step 2: Now, we show that if $Y = X$, then T and f have a unique common fixed point.

$Tu = fu$, and T and f commute at their coincidence point u , hence $TTu = Tfu = fTu = ffu$. Therefore, if one supposes that $Tu \neq TTu$, then $N(u, Tu) > 0$ and

$$D(Tu, TTu) \leq cN(u, Tu) = cD(Tu, TTu),$$

a contradiction. Therefore $D(Tu, TTu) = 0$ and $TTu = Tu = fTu$: Tu is a common fixed point of T and f .

Step 3: To show that $z := Tu$ is the only common fixed point of T and f , suppose v is another a common fixed point of the pair $\{T, f\}$. We have that $z \neq u$ so $N(z, v) > 0$ and

$$D(z, v) = D(Tz, Tv) \leq cN(z, v) = cD(z, v),$$

a contradiction. Thus $D(z, v) = 0$ and $z = v$. □

The following corollary holds in metric spaces:

Corollary 3.2. *Let (X, d) be a metric space and $T, f : Y \rightarrow X$ mappings such that $T(Y) \subseteq f(Y)$. Suppose also that there is $c \in (0, 1)$ such that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x, y \in Y$ with $M(x, y) > 0$,*

$$d(u, v) \leq cM(x, y) \tag{3.12}$$

for any $u \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx)$ and $v \in (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)$, where

$$M(x, y) = \max \{d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), d(fx, Ty), d(fy, Tx)\}. \tag{3.13}$$

If $T(Y)$ or $f(Y)$ is $\{T, f\}$ -orbitally complete, then T and f have a coincidence point. Further, if $Y = X$, then T and f have a unique common fixed point provided that T and f commute at a coincidence point.

4 Example

To validate the results obtained, we construct the following example of the applicability of Theorem 2.5.

Example 4.1. *Let $X = [1, 2]$ be equipped with the usual metric $d(x, y) = |x - y|$. Let $T, f : X \rightarrow X$ be defined by: $Tx = \frac{x+2}{3}$ and $fx = \frac{x+1}{2}$ for all $x \in [1, 2]$. Here, $T(X) = [1, \frac{4}{3}]$ and $f(X) = [1, \frac{3}{2}]$ hence $T(X) \subset f(X)$. Here, f is bijective, and $f^{-1}(x) = 2x - 1$ for all $x \in [1, \frac{3}{2}]$. Therefore, $(Tf^{-1})(x) = \frac{2x+1}{3}$ for all $x \in [1, \frac{3}{2}]$ and for all $n \geq 0$, $(Tf^{-1})^n(x) = (\frac{2}{3})^n(x-1) + 1$ for all $x \in [1, \frac{3}{2}]$.*

$$(Tf^{-1})^n(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x = 1, \\ (\frac{2}{3})^n(x-1) + 1 & \text{if } x \in (1, \frac{3}{2}], \end{cases}$$

One can check that for all $n \geq 1$, and $x, y \in [1, \frac{3}{2}]$,

$$d((Tf^{-1})^n(x), (Tf^{-1})^n(y)) = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^n |x - y|.$$

In particular, for all $n \geq 0$ and $x, y \in [1, 2]$,

$$d((Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx), (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)) = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{n-1} \left| \frac{x-y}{3} \right|.$$

Moreover, $d(fx, fy) = \frac{1}{2}|x - y|$ for $x \in [1, 2]$. Therefore, for all $x, y \in [1, 2]$ such that $M(x, y) > 0$,

$$d((Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Tx), (Tf^{-1})^{n-1}(Ty)) = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^n d(fx, fy) < \psi_n(M(x, y)),$$

where

$$\psi_n(t) = 2 \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^n t \quad \forall t \geq 0.$$

One can check that $\{\psi_n\}$ satisfies conditions (G_1) and (G_2) of Theorem 2.5 since for all $\epsilon \geq 0$, $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi_n(\epsilon) = 0 \leq \epsilon$, and if $\epsilon > 0$, $\delta = \frac{\epsilon}{8}$, and $\nu = 2$, then $\psi_\nu(t) \leq \epsilon$ for all $t \in [\epsilon, \epsilon + \delta]$.

In addition, T and f commute at their only coincidence point $x = 1$ hence all the conditions of Theorem 2.5 hold. Therefore, T and f have a unique common fixed point. It is easily seen that $x = 1$ is the only common fixed point of T and f . Given $x_0 \in [1, 2]$, consider the Jungck sequence $Tx_n = fx_{n+1}$. In the uninteresting case that $x_0 = 1$, $x_n = 1$ for any $n \geq 1$. Now, let $x_0 \in (1, 2]$. Then $3x_{n+1} = 2x_n + 1$ for all $n \geq 0$. A quick computation gives the following formula for any $n \geq 1$:

$$x_n = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^n (x_0 - 1) + 1$$

$$Tx_n = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^n (x_0 - 1) + 1.$$

Thus $\{Tx_n\}$ converges to $T(1) = 1$, the common fixed point of the pair $\{T, f\}$.

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